

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HAMANDAWANA****FIRST NAME: YGAINNIA****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: MSWord Office 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the following is not a set of rules of thumb for writing a paper?
 - Precisely stating the paper's central argument at the beginning, focusing on the paper's topic, avoiding going off on tangents, avoiding broad generalizations at the beginning or end, writing in a clear and concise style, and supporting claims with evidence from reliable sources.
 - Considering the views of others seriously, even if in disagreement, avoiding copying the work of others without giving credit, carefully proofreading the paper before submitting it, using the first-person singular pronoun "I" in the paper, and properly citing sources.

- Choosing a topic of interest and knowledge, gathering evidence to support claims, organizing ideas logically, writing a draft of the paper and revising it carefully, and proofreading the final draft before submitting it.**¹
- Use of short sentences and paragraphs, use of transition words and phrases to show how ideas are connected, avoiding passive voice and long strings of prepositional phrases, use of a variety of sentence structures and stylistic variety, and avoiding word repetitions over and over.
2. Which of the following is not a characteristic of a good paraphrase?
- It accurately conveys the original text's meaning in the writer's words.
- It uses quotation marks.**²
- It uses a different sentence structure and vocabulary than the original text.
- It is shorter than the original text.
3. According to Turabian of Chicago guidelines, which criterion is a source not evaluated for reliability?
- The recency of the edition of the source.**³
- Impact factor.
- Author's reputation.

¹ Laurent Cleenerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 4th ed. (Bangui: EUCLID University, 2021), 12–14.

² *Ibid.*, 34–36.

³ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 23–24.

- Punctuation, grammar, or spelling errors.
4. Using Turabian notes-style citation, how is a source not mentioned in the text but essential to understanding the topic referenced?
- Use a footnote to indicate the author's name, the title of the publication, place of publication, publisher, year of publication, and page number or range of pages.
- Use a source line to indicate the author's name, the title of the publication, place of publication, publisher, year of publication, and page number or range of pages.
- Use a bibliography entry to list the source.**⁴
- Use a parenthetical citation in the text to indicate the author's name, the title of the publication, place of publication, publisher, year of publication, and page number or range of pages.
5. Which of these statements about the relationship between the research problem, research purpose, and research questions is false?
- The research problem and research purpose contain similar information.
- The research purpose is an extension of the research problem.
- The research purpose is the primary objective or intent of the study.
- Preliminary data collected on the research questions can help refine the research purpose and problem.**⁵

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 124.

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publishers, 2019), 182–184.

6. Which of the following is not beneficial to having a well-defined theoretical or conceptual framework in research?
- It provides a simple algorithm for all data analysis across varied research questions, methodologies, and data types.⁶**
 - It helps to sieve through the data and identify the most critical features of the research and the relationships that are likely to be significant.
 - It helps to ground the study in existing knowledge and situate it within a scholarly conversation.
 - It provides a lens through which to interpret the data and identify patterns.
7. What statement best describes the difference between conceptual and relational analysis in content analysis?
- Conceptual analysis is a deductive approach, while relational analysis is an inductive approach.
 - Conceptual analysis focuses on the presence or absence of certain words or phrases in a text, while relational analysis focuses on the relationships between different concepts in a text.⁷**
 - Conceptual analysis is used to analyze the manifest content of a text, while relational analysis is used to analyze the latent content of a text.
 - Conceptual analysis is used to identify the main themes in a text, while relational analysis is used to identify the relationships between different themes.

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 339–342.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 491–492.

8. Which of the following is not beneficial for organizing a dissertation according to a procedural schema?
- It helps the researcher to understand the order of steps needed to finish a complex task.
 - It allows the researcher to understand how new knowledge gained by completing one task becomes antecedent knowledge for completing the next task.
 - It helps ensure that the dissertation is well-organized and very easy to read.**⁸
 - It enables the reader to understand the logical flow of the dissertation, from the design and execution of the research to the meaning of the findings.
9. Which of the following is recommended by the European Union for any explanations for tables at their foot?
- Use of a lower-case superscript number followed by the relevant text.
 - Use of the word Note in italics, followed by a colon and relevant text.
 - Use of a single asterisk followed by the relevant text.
 - Use of NB followed by the relevant text.**⁹
10. What numbering format would a legal act published on 1 September 1997 assume per European Union guidelines?

⁸ James Sampson Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 16–17.

⁹ European Union, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (Brussels: European Union, 2021), 60.

- 97/12.¹⁰
- 1997/12.
- 12/97.
- 12/1997.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation. A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publishers, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. Bangui: EUCLID University, 2021.

European Union. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 8th ed. Brussels: European Union, 2021.

Sampson Jr., James. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Florida: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ European Union, *English Style Guide*, 78.